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Theoretical and Experimental Analysis of single-arm bimodal Plasmo-Photonic refractive index sensors

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Abstract:

In this paper, we study both theoretically and experimentally the sensitivity of bimodal interferometric sensors where interference occurs between modes with different properties propagating in the same physical waveguide. In contrast to the well-known Mach-Zehnder interferometric (MZI) sensors, we show for the first time that the sensitivity of the bimodal sensors is independent of the sensing area length. This is validated by applying the theory to an integrated plasmo-photonic bimodal sensor that comprises an Aluminum (Al) plasmonic stripe waveguide co-integrated between two access SU-8 photonic waveguides. A series of such bimodal sensors utilizing plasmonic stripes of different lengths were numerically simulated demonstrating bulk refractive index (RI) sensitivities around 5700 nm/RIU for all sensor variants confirming the theoretical results. The theoretical and numerical results were also validated experimentally through chip-level RI sensing experiments on three fabricated SU-8/Al bimodal sensors with plasmonic sensing lengths of 50, 75 and 100 μm . The obtained experimental RI sensitivities were found to be very close and equal to 4464, 4386 and 4362 nm/RIU, respectively, confirming that the sensing length has no effect on the bimodal sensor sensitivity. The above outcome alleviates the design and optical loss constraints paving the way for more compact and powerful sensors that can achieve high sensitivity values at ultra-short sensing lengths.

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1. Introduction

Nowadays, there is a great need for the development of novel refractive index (RI) sensors that can replace the expensive and time-consuming laboratory techniques with fast and user-friendly portable devices. Among the technologies under consideration, integrated photonic sensors have attracted the interest of the scientific community [1], because they offer several advantages including: (i) high sensitivity, (ii) real-time and label-free operation, and (iii) mass production at a low-cost. Although photonic biosensors have already been commercialized, their sensitivity performance is inherently constrained by the partial exposure of the propagating mode to the sample under investigation, which necessitates the use of long sensor lengths in the range of several millimeters or even centimeters,

severely impacting device compactness and the number of sensing elements that can be hosted on a single chip.

Plasmonic sensors have been proposed as an alternative sensing platform that can offer higher sensitivity values while retaining a short transducer length [5], [6] as this takes advantage of the exposure of the entire plasmonic mode to the surrounding medium. On the other hand, the inevitable high propagation losses introduced by plasmonic structures can be partially counterbalanced by the selective co-integration of plasmonic segments in low-loss photonic integrated circuits, combining in this way the advantages of both technologies. So far, several works demonstrating plasmo-photonic sensors in either Mach Zehnder interferometer (MZI) or ring configurations have been reported [7]. MZIs are more tolerant and flexible structures that can be easily engineered to provide higher sensitivity values. However, the need for two spatially separated optical paths increases the required footprint and the calibration complexity, as both arms have to be configured for optimal interference conditions prior to the injection of the liquid analyte. In an attempt to miniaturize interferometric sensing devices, single path interferometers exploiting modes of different properties that propagate in the same physical channel, known as bimodal interferometers, have been investigated [10]. Although these single arm interferometric structures have been shown to provide moderate sensitivity values that can be valuable in certain applications, a compact and comprehensive theoretical model that can associate their sensitivity capabilities with the material and geometrical characteristics of the device is still missing, impeding in this way any sensor optimization concepts.

In this article, we extend our previous experimental work reported in [16] and present a holistic theoretical and experimental analysis of bimodal single-arm interferometric sensors, concluding to a closed mathematical expression for their sensitivity and its relation to sensor length and material platform. Based on this analysis, the sensitivity of a bimodal sensors turns to be independent of the detection area length and depends only on the difference between the group indices of the two propagating modes. These findings are verified both numerically and experimentally using a plasmo-photonic bimodal sensor that employs an Aluminum (Al) plasmonic stripe co-integrated on a SU-8 photonic platform. The length-independent sensing performance of single-arm bimodal interferometers highlights an additional important advantage for this type of sensors, on top of their well-known single-path and as such compact and higher environmental perturbation tolerance properties: it relieves sensitivity improvements from the need for using longer sensing lengths and higher sensor footprints. Instead, it can sustain higher sensitivities only by appropriately engineering the group indices of the two propagating modes while maintaining an ultra-short detection area. This can significantly contribute towards low optical losses by providing the flexibility of using shorter transducer lengths without sacrificing sensor sensitivity, which is especially critical when plasmonic sensing waveguides (WGs) are employed.

2. Theoretical analysis

In principle, the bulk RI sensitivity (S_b) of an optical sensor operating with spectral interrogation is defined by the amount of wavelength shift, $\Delta\lambda_{dip/peak}^k$, caused by the effective index change of the mode propagating along the sensing waveguide due to a change in the ambient refractive index. The sensitivity is expressed in units (nm/RIU). According to the analysis presented in [17], for an interferometric sensor, this wavelength shift, and consequently, sensitivity is given by the following compact equation:

$$S_b = \Delta\lambda_{dip/peak} = \frac{L_{sen} \lambda_{dip/peak}}{\Delta(n_g L)} \quad (1)$$

where L_{sen} represents the corresponding length of the sensing waveguide, $\lambda_{dip/peak}$ is the wavelength dip or peak and $\Delta(n_g L)$ for a conventional MZI is equal to:

$$\Delta(n_g L) = n_{g,ref} L_{ref} - n_{g,sen} L_{sen} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1. (a) Conceptual schematic of the bimodal refractive index sensor, (b) cross-section of the input SU-8 photonic WG with the fabricated dimensions, (c) cross-sectional dimensions of the aluminum plasmonic WG, (d), (e) side view and top view of the presented device, respectively.

where $n_{g,ref}$ and $n_{g,sen}$ are the group indices of the modes propagating in the reference and the sensing arm, respectively, and L_{ref} and L_{sen} are the length of the reference and of the sensing arms, respectively. A bimodal configuration consists of one physical path and for this reason the length of the two optical paths is equal ($L_{ref} = L_{sen}$)

So, the equation (2) is simplified to:

$$\Delta(n_g L) = L_{sen}(n_{g,ref} - n_{g,sen}) \quad (3)$$

Replacing equation (3) in (1), the S_b is calculated according to the following equation:

$$S_b = \frac{\lambda_{dip/peak}}{n_{g,ref} - n_{g,sen}} \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) shows that the sensitivity of bimodal interferometric sensors is independent of the sensing area length. At first view, this result might seem counter-intuitive: increasing the sensing length (L_{sen}) in an interferometric device, the accumulating phase shift of the mode propagating along the sensing waveguide increases, which increases the wavelength shift at the output and, thus should, the sensitivity. However, to explain the physical phenomenon behind this behaviour, we should also consider that the amount of phase shift (in units of 2π) required for a unit wavelength shift, determined by the inverse of the FSR, also increases by the same proportion. Specifically, the equation that gives the FSR of the bimodal interferometer:

$$FSR = \frac{\lambda^2}{\Delta(n_g L)} = \frac{\lambda^2}{L_{sen} \Delta(n_g)} \quad (5)$$

we observe that the FSR is inversely proportional to L_{sen} . Thus, the increase of the sensing length causes an FSR decrease, which reduces the sensitivity since a certain phase shift of the propagating mode now corresponds to a smaller wavelength shift (a full FSR corresponds to 2π phase shift). Consequently, sensitivity remains constant regardless of the sensing length.

From another point of view, we can express the sensitivity as a function of FSR:

$$S_b = \frac{\lambda}{\lambda^2} = \frac{L_{sen} FSR}{\lambda} \quad (6)$$

According to equation (6), the sensitivity increases with increasing L_{sen} . However, according to equation (5), the FSR decreases with increasing L_{sen} which in turn decreases the sensitivity according to equation (6). So, the sensing length has a contradictory effect on sensitivity which finally remains constant irrespective of the sensing length.

On the contrary, in a conventional MZI the FSR is given by the following equation:

$$FSR = \frac{\lambda^2}{\Delta(n_g L)} = \frac{\lambda^2}{n_{g,ref} L_{ref} - n_{g,sen} L_{sen}} \quad (7)$$

And the sensitivity is given by:

$$S_b = \frac{L_{sen} \cdot FSR}{\lambda} = \frac{L_{sen} \cdot \frac{\lambda^2}{n_{g,ref} L_{ref} - n_{g,sen} L_{sen}}}{\lambda} \Rightarrow$$

$$S_b = \frac{L_{sen} \cdot \lambda}{n_{g,ref} L_{ref} - n_{g,sen} L_{sen}} \quad (8)$$

So, in this case the FSR depends not only on the length of the sensing arm but also on the length of the reference arm and their group index difference. Consequently, in the equation that gives the sensitivity, L_{sen} is not eliminated and thus, sensitivity increases with increasing L_{sen} .

3. Numerical validation

The integrated bimodal sensor under investigation consists of two photonic waveguides (WG) based on SU-8 material forming the input and output of the device, and an Al plasmonic stripe WG that is placed between them and on top of a suitably thinner SU-8 WG, named as bottom SU-8 layer. Figure 1(a) depicts the 3D conceptual schematic of the studied plasmophotonic bimodal sensor while Figure 1(d) and Figure 1(e) show the side- and top view of the structure, respectively. The plasmonic WG supports two different surface plasmon polariton (SPP) modes: (i) the top mode at the interface between the Al stripe and the surrounding medium which plays the role of the sensing branch, and (ii) the bottom mode at the interface between the Al stripe and the bottom SU-8 layer which plays the role of the reference branch. These modes are excited by a fundamental TM photonic mode launched in the input SU-8 WG and, after propagating along the metal surfaces, interfere at the output photonic part realizing in this way the single-arm interferometer.

A $1.8 \mu\text{m} \times 1.5 \mu\text{m}$ (thickness \times width) SU-8 ($n_{\text{SU-8}} = 1.575 - 0.0001j$) strip WG core lying on top of a silicon oxide (SiO_2) substrate was employed for the input and output photonic waveguides. The waveguides were not cladded and were exposed to the ambient. The cross section of the photonic WG along with the supported TM mode profile are depicted in Figure 1(b) and Figure 1(a)(i), respectively. The plasmonic WG is formed by depositing an $80 \text{ nm} \times 7 \mu\text{m}$ aluminum ($n_{\text{Al}} = 1.427 - 15.135j$) **Σφάλμα! Το αρχείο προέλευσης της αναφοράς δεν βρέθηκε.** stripe on top of the bottom SU-8 layer with the same width. The cross-sectional dimensions of the Al-on-SU-8 WG along with the mode profiles of the top and bottom plasmonic modes are presented in Figure 1(c), Figure 1(a)(ii) and Figure 1(a)(iii). For the above dimensions and a bottom layer with $0.9 \mu\text{m}$ thickness, the effective and group indices obtained with 2D eigenvalue analysis are: $n_{\text{eff,top}} = 1.31$ for the top and $n_{\text{eff,bottom}} = 1.575$ for the bottom mode, and $n_{\text{group,top}} = 1.36$ for the top and $n_{\text{group,bottom}} = 1.62$ for

Figure 2: Simulated bimodal transfer function and sensitivity measurements for plasmonic length (a) $100 \mu\text{m}$, (b) $75 \mu\text{m}$ and (c) $50 \mu\text{m}$, respectively.

the bottom mode at $\lambda = 1550$ nm. The exact, optimum dimensions were defined based on a systematic design analysis targeting: (i) maximum RI sensitivity and (ii) maximum extinction ratio (ER) at the sensor output that allows lower detection limits. In order to achieve the maximum ER, the thickness of the bottom SU-8 layer was thoroughly investigated in combination with the appropriate plasmonic stripe length aiming at optimal interference conditions between the two plasmonic modes at the sensor output. The detailed design analysis is described in [16]. According to Eq. (4), the theoretical sensitivity (S_b) of the above bimodal sensor is 5961 nm/RIU at $\lambda = 1550$ nm.

The numerical evaluation of the above bimodal sensor was conducted by means of circuit level simulations using the INTERCONNECT photonic integrated circuit simulator of Ansys Lumerical. Three different structures with plasmonic lengths of 100, 75 and 50 μm were simulated in order to evaluate their sensitivity and how it is affected by the length of the plasmonic sensing area. Water cladding has been considered on top of the plasmonic stripe with an RI value obtained from literature ($n_{\text{water}} = 1.311 - 0.0001348j @ 1550$ nm [18]). The corresponding simulation curves are depicted in Figure 2 (a)-(c). As expected from the theory described above, the numerical sensitivity measurements revealed a bulk RI sensitivity of ± 5723 nm/RIU for all plasmonic lengths, validating that the sensitivity of the bimodal sensor is independent of the sensing length.

Figure 3: Top view microscope image of fabricated plasmonic waveguides of different lengths.

4. Fabrication

The proposed sensor was fabricated on 150 nm Si substrate containing a 3 μm thick thermally grown SiO_2 layer. The first SU-8 layer was spin-coated on the entire wafer and a two-stage soft-bake process on hot-plates was followed. The structures were exposed with

Figure 4: (a) Schematic of the experimental setup, (b) photo from the probe station used for optical characterization and refractive index experiments.

Figure 5: Experimental measurements versus wavelength for different plasmonic waveguide lengths in air condition, (a) 100 μm sensor, (b) 75 μm sensor and (c) 50 μm sensor.

optical i-line stepper lithography. Afterwards, the wafer underwent a hard-bake process to cross-link the resist, resulting in the formation of the bottom SU-8 layer (referred as bottom SU-8 layer) with a measured thickness of 0.9 μm . The hard bake process ensured the mechanical and chemical stability of the fabrication of the WGs. After completing the fabrication of the bottom SU-8 layer, the Al layer was deposited using electron beam evaporator resulting in plasmonic stripe WG. More specifically, a layer with 80 nm thickness was deposited onto the underlying SU-8. Another i-line lithography process was used for the patterning of the metal layer. The process flow of the second (top) SU-8 layer was very similar to the one described above. However, the deposition and exposure parameters were optimised considering the topography generated after the fabrication of the top SU-8 layer. Figure 3 depicts a microscope top-view image of the fabricated sensors showing varying Al length. To form the coupling edge required for butt-coupling, the wafer was diced down into 2 cm \times 2 cm chips by gently sawing through the SU-8 WGs.

5. Experimental results

Figure 4(a) shows the experimental setup used to evaluate the sensors. The setup consists of the following components: a tunable laser source (TLS) that emits light from 1500 nm to 1630 nm with a resolution of 100 pm, a lensed polarization maintaining fiber, the integrated sensors with different plasmonic lengths and an optical power meter. The light emitted by the TLS, through the lensed fiber at the input, was injected into the chip in TM polarity. Butt/edge coupling scheme was used for the optical in- and out-coupling.

The first characterization step to perform sensitivity measurements for the different plasmonic sensors was the optical characterization of the sensors in air. Figure 5(a)-(c) shows the experimental spectra obtained for three different plasmonic lengths (i.e. 100, 75 and 50 μm). In each spectrum of the above plasmonic structures a Fast Fourier Filter was applied, as mentioned also in [19] to better identify the interferometric response and track the performance of the structures. It can be clearly seen that the experimentally observed FRS

Figure 6: Experimental sensor spectral response when using different liquid samples with refractive index varying from 1.3340 to 1.3573 for different Al stripe length (a) 100 μm , (b) 75 μm and (c) 50 μm , respectively.

Figure 7: Resonance shift with respect to the refractive index change of the different solutions and least-squares linear fit for the different plasmonic waveguide lengths for (a) simulated data and (b) experimental measurements, (c) comparison in sensitivity values for different plasmonic length and extracting the data from mathematical equations, from interconnect and from experiment and the overall losses for different plasmonic stripe lengths.

values are in good agreement with the values expected from theory, confirming the bimodal operation. 220

After completing the optical characterization of the sensors in air, the sensitivity experiments were conducted to evaluate the operation of the plasmo-photonic structures as an R.I sensor. The sensitivity measurements were performed by spraying droplets of 4 different aqueous solutions over the plasmonic sensor region as depicted in the inset in Figure 4. A commercial refractometer manufactured by Mettler Toledo company was used to determine the RI of the samples, resulting in RI values between 1.3340 and 1.3573. 222 223 224 225 226 227

Figure 6(a)-(c) presents the smoothed measured sensor spectra when the sensor surface is covered by the liquid solutions, revealing a clear blue-shift of the resonance dip/peak with increasing RI values. Bulk sensitivity values were calculated for the resonance dip/peak (as indicated by the arrows in the plots in Figure 6) by performing linear least squares fit to the wavelength dip/peak with increasing RI values, as shown in Figure 7(a) and (b) for the experimental and simulated values, respectively. Using this method, we calculated the RI sensitivity for plasmonic lengths of 100, 75 and 50 μm and we obtained the sensitivity values of 4464, 4386 and 4362 nm/RIU, respectively. The above experimental sensitivity values reveal strong agreement not only with the theory (5961 nm/RIU), but also with the corresponding values of about 5723 nm/RIU that were derived from the INTERCONNECT software. The left axis of Figure 7(c) depicts a comparison of the sensitivities between the experimental values, the values from INTERCONNECT and the values expected from theory, while the right axis of the same figure presents the overall experimental losses of the sensor for different plasmonic waveguide lengths. According to Figure 7(c) the sensitivity of the proposed sensor remains stable and doesn't depend on the detection area length, while the overall transmission losses reduce for shorter plasmonic WG lengths. 228 229 230 231 232 233 234 235 236 237 238 239 240 241 242 243

Based on the above theoretical analysis, the experimental results presented in Figure 6 and the comparison in Figure 7(c), the plasmonic length has no effect on the sensitivity of an interferometric sensor when based on a single-arm bimodal configuration. By excluding the plasmonic length as a parameter to increase the sensitivity, it is possible to increase the transmission with shorter stripes lengths, helping the signal to noise ration and reducing system cost, leading to an improvement of the overall performance of the proposed sensor. 244 245 246 247 248 249 250

Conclusions 251

We theoretically investigated the sensitivity of bimodal interferometric sensors concluding to a mathematical equation for its calculation which shows that the sensing element length has no influence on their sensitivity. We validated the theory both numerically and experimentally utilizing a plasmo-photonic interferometric bimodal sensor based on an Al-on-SU8 bimodal structure with lengths of 100, 75 and 50 μm . In all cases, the sensitivity remained almost constant with the experimental (4464, 4386 and 4362 nm/RIU), the numerical (5723 nm/RIU) and the theoretical (5961 nm/RIU) values being in very good agreement. Proving 252 253 254 255 256 257 258

that the sensitivity of bimodal interferometric sensors remains constant irrespective of the plasmonic sensing transducer length, we open up new possibilities for ultra-compact and highly sensitive sensors keeping the overall losses at a low level.

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